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D2.9 Final version of user requirements

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D2.9 Final version of user requirements

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Author name(s):	Vasiliki Pavlidou (AUTH), Ilias Machairas (AUTH), Despoina Petsani (AUTH), Michalis Timoleon (AUTH)	
Contributor(s):	Adriane Thrash (AV), Paraskevi Giourka (AV), Argyris Spyridis (AV), Omer Onur (ENoLL), Francisco Londoño (VICOM), Vicky Fiska (CERTH), Gorka Epelde (VICOM)	
Reviewer(s):	Chrstoniki Maga (CERTH)	Pieter Van Gorp (TUE)
Approved by:	Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Project Coordinator	
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The **VITALISE** Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	ENoLL	Belgium
2	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Greece
3	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	LAUREA	Finland
4	THOMAS MORE KEMPEN VZW	LICALAB	Belgium
5	FUNDACION INTRAS	INTRAS	Spain
6	TREBAG SZELLEMI TULAJDON- ES PROJEKTMENEDZSER KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG	TREBAG	Hungary
7	ASOCIACION DE INDUSTRIAS DE CONOCIMIENTO Y TECNOLOGIA - GAIA - EUSKALHERRIKO EZAGUTZA ETA TEKNOLOGIA INDUSTRIEN ELKARTEA	GAIA	Spain
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	Spain
9	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	Greece
10	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	AIT	Austria
11	SOCIALIT SOFTWARE E CONSULTING SRL	SIT	Italy
12	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain
13	WITA SRL	WITA	Italy
14	ANTHOLOGY VENTURES JSC	AV	Bulgaria
15	VILABS OE	VILABS	Greece
16	FORUM DES LIVING LABS EN SANTE ET AUTONOMIE	LLSA	France
17	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT INDHOVEN	TUE	Netherlands
18	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	McGill	Canada
19	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	UDEM	Canada

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Executive summary

The VITALISE ICT tools should provide convenient access to researchers. Therefore, the development of such tools should be based on well established user requirements. Within VITALISE, we have adopted an iterative and agile spiral model approach to ensure rapid feedback and gradual improvements. This document presents the User requirements that have been collected until M24 and that have provided insights and guidance to the developers of the ICT tools, under WP3. Requirements were explored on the topic curation and access of the datasets, user interface (UI) expectations, and more generally the expected functionality of the tools. In order to achieve eventual user acceptance, a multimethod approach was followed, tailoring the requirement elicitation methods to part of the ICT tool suite. These methods included a number of workshops, a literature review, ICT tools demonstrations, and live experimentation.

This document is the final version of the ICT tools user requirements and provides an overview of the requirements that are already implemented in the systems or are planned to be delivered until the end of the project. This deliverable provides an overview of the final system for all VITALISE ICT tools from the user perspective. It presents information about the Panel Management tool (the PaneLab), the AccelUp system for the uptake of Living Lab services by the Research and Innovation community, the RAI system for data analysis and sharing that will support also VITALISE Virtual Access and the newly added Sensors' Integration system that is built to support the day-to-day research activities and data acquisition in Living Labs. It also includes information about the methodology used for requirement elicitation.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose document

VITALISE designs and develops ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets in order to facilitate access to data and technology for researchers in Living Lab research infrastructures. Moreover, VITALISE builds ICT tools and e-infrastructures that will be used by Living Lab researchers and will help harmonize and optimize their work. In the first version of this deliverable (D2.8), three main VITALISE software tools are being described: the panel management, the Accellup system and the RAI system and Discovery portal. Based on the needs of VITALISE partners and external researchers, the RAI system and Discovery portal is extended in order to support also the data acquisition domain. For this purpose, this deliverable extends D2.8 by also presenting a fourth VITALISE ICT software tool, related to Sensors Integration.

This document analyzes and presents the final version of the user requirements for the four systems. The goal is to present the actual requirements that are already implemented or will be implemented by the end of the project. VITALISE consortium will keep updating the requirements list. All the requirements that will not be delivered during the project lifecycle, will feed the exploitation plan for each ICT tool. The requirement elicitation procedures were based on co-design principles, involving the VITALISE consortium and external researchers in the process. Furthermore, the current version of the tools depicts also the long-term acquired experience of the three participating Living Lab networks, ENOLL, EIT Living Labs and Forum LLSA.

1.2 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the purpose of the document and makes an introduction on the drivers for the creations of the ICT tools.
- **Section 2** presents the updates and final version of requirements for the panel management tool.
- **Section 3** does the same for the AccelUp tool.
- **Section 4** does that for the RAI system and discovery portal.
- **Section 5** presents a new component for more convenient system integration.
- **Section 6** provides the concluding remarks for this deliverable

1.3 The need for ICT tools for Living Labs

Panel management

“Panel management” as a term is used both in healthcare and business to refer to the coordination and research of a group of people that receive services from an organization. The group of people can refer to the population of patients that receive care from a healthcare facility or the group of customers for a company.

Living Labs have adopted the term panel management to refer to a pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g., patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. As panel and systematic user involvement are some of the Living Labs building blocks (Veeckman et al., 2013), efficient panel management is of high importance. The panel-based approach requires a permanent Living Lab infrastructure, as opposed to one-shot panels. Maintaining thematically themed panels of profiled users yields many benefits for the management of Living Lab research and innovation processes (Schuurman & De Marez, 2012).

A well-planned panel management process allows the Living Lab to create meaningful activities and sustainable processes for the involvement of the different stakeholders. Such activities include

frequent communications (e.g., mailing bi-monthly newsletters, sharing results and pictures of the projects) and interactions among the wider network of all stakeholders who need to be involved. Panel processes prescribe how, when, where and which are these stakeholders fulfill a role in the panel.

For an example of a thematically themed panel, consider a health-related Living Lab. Within such a living lab, older adults, their caregivers, families and general practitioners are typically included as well. Moreover, a survey on the motivations for collaboration showed that intrinsic motivations were highest among the panel members, meaning that panel members had a personal interest in making a valuable contribution to the innovation.

The use of an ICT tool for panel management means a strong decrease in time and effort required by panel managers. In particular, such a tool enables living lab processes to planned and tracked for in a systematic way.

AccelUp system

One of the goals of VITALISE is to promote the scalability and exploitation of Health and Wellbeing Living Labs services, as well as Non-Health and Wellbeing Living Lab services, at the local, trans-regional, and trans-national levels to support research and entrepreneurial products and services in the domain. While Living Lab research and real environment testing infrastructures are crucial for researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain, Living Labs struggle to receive offers for private projects beyond their network. This is due to the high amount of resources required for a living lab to be visible beyond its network. Furthermore, Living Labs often do not know how much to charge for their services, which makes it challenging for researchers and research groups to understand the cost of a Living Lab service and the extent of what a Living Lab can offer. These problems have been identified by ENoLL and the Health and Wellbeing Action Oriented Task Force during meetups and individual discussions with Living Lab members.

The proposed AccelUp system aims to increase the visibility of Living Lab research and testing infrastructures and their services to attract researchers, entrepreneurs, and private companies. This would enable Living Labs to grow their activities, create a more sustainable business model, and develop a portfolio of completed jobs. They would also gain insights on the prices of their services, which would help stabilize demand and offer prices. On the other hand, customers of Living Labs would be able to receive qualified feedback regarding their research and/or products and services and obtain a Living Lab certification that attaches a quality and reliability image to their products and services.

RAI system and Discovery portal

Open data sharing has gained great momentum with funding agencies as well as with publishers. The Transparency and Openness Promotion (TOP) Guidelines describe for all such stakeholders how to promote transparency, openness and reproducibility (Nosek, 2016). Already a few years after the publication of the guidelines, hundreds of publishers and journals — including Elsevier and Springer Nature — had signed up to the TOP guidelines (Gewin, 2016). This movement aims to counter the reproducibility crisis, as originally reported in fields like psychology (Aarts et al., 2015), but more recently also in the domains of digital medicine (Stupple et al., 2019) and artificial intelligence (Hutson, 2018)

Still, contemporary researchers find it difficult to get access to high quality data, or safe means to share such data. For example, in a Living Lab setting, data owners will not provide access without a non-disclosure agreement or reassurance given that trust and ethics are basic consideration in Living Labs methodological guidelines. While several existing communities for Medical Infrastructures are gaining popularity (e.g., the European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine (EATRIS) and the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN)), their scope is limited to the (bio-)medical disciplines such as vaccine and drug development, or translational medicine. Within VITALISE, we aim to provide similar support to those scholars who seek or want to provide access to high quality data related to studies in ambulatory settings, in rehab centers, recreational spaces like gyms, and even citizens participating in studies where data is collected continuously. Sharing

data from such studies is complicated, as acknowledged by a systematic review by van Panhuis et al. (Van Panhuis et al., 2014). That study lists 7 technical barriers, such as “Technical solutions not available”. The article clarifies that such solutions are critical to collect, harmonize (transformation and recoding to enhance inter-operability), integrate (combining harmonized datasets), and share complex and heterogeneous data. Within VITALISE, we aim to fill that gap specifically for data collected in a Living Lab setting. The Van Panhuis review lists various other barriers, including political and legal ones, such as “Lack of trust” and “Protection of privacy”. Within VITALISE such barriers were considered in the requirements analysis for the data sharing platform.

The building of this type of digital infrastructures has been recommended also by a 2018 European Commission Expert group on FAIR data (European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data, 2018). Specifically, the second out of the seven recommendations were to develop better “FAIR ecosystems”. Basic ecosystem features include the issuing of digital object identifiers (DOIs) for data sets are becoming mainstream. For example, the figshare.com website has facilitated over 30,000 citations of data to date. However, such websites do not yet provide features that address the trust and privacy barriers mentioned above.

With these guidelines and recommendations in mind, the RAI system was conceived and developed to address some of these challenges. The proposed RAI system has 3 main components interconnected: a RAI Node, the Discovery Portal and the RAI Cloud Server. The RAI Node is projected to be locally installed, allowing Researchers, and LLs personnel in general, to interact with the system from a local perspective, preserving the ownership of the data. The RAI Node functionalities include the possibility of: (1) registering datasets and subjects, assigning a unique identifier to them, (2) uploading data (specific types/formats), (3) exploring datasets, (4) requesting anonymised or synthetic data, among other possibilities. The Discovery Portal is conceived as a central hub where researchers (external to each LL) can explore available datasets, request data, and perform remote execution of processing scripts on selected datasets without a direct access to raw (and potentially sensitive) data. The RAI Cloud Server acts as a background system to preserve results and executions of processed datasets so experiments can be retrieved, ensuring reproducibility and traceability. A detailed description of functionalities is included in section 5.2 of this document.

Sensors Integration Server

Integration of sensors is an important topic in automation systems, and terms such as *flexibility*, *reduced setup time*, *parametrisation through software components*, *configurability*, *UI simplicity* (Scheibelmasser et al., 2006) appear in this context, regardless of the field of application. The need to offer Living Lab researchers and practitioners the infrastructure to conduct their experiments in an effective way, lead to the development of a single page application, where the devices provided by the LL, are accompanied by their respective software, allowing, with minimal effort, their utilisation.

The purpose of the developed application is to enable Living Lab researchers to connect the devices used in Living Lab environment and collect data in central repositories of the Living Lab. New devices can be added with the creation and upload of device drivers (or plugins) that enable the extension of functionalities. The datasets gathered are also seamlessly uploaded in the connected LL RAI node. The Server is agnostic to the drivers used, requiring only a standardised format and relative information regarding the type of the plugin (whether it is an executable or a script) and the device UUID. Optional arguments might be provided as input such as configuration fields, including but not limited to, duration of measurement gathering and device BLE address specification.

The prototype developed, consists of 4 parts in the main page, namely the “Tools” part for managing plugin uploads and the broker settings (for information on the broker, see Section 5), and the rest of the page is divided for available, configured and running plugins. The configurations contain information on specifics for a plugin, such as run time, information about subject etc.

2 Panel Management

Panel management is one of the identified services, provided by a Living Lab (<https://wiki.livinglab-harmonization.com/xwiki/bin/view/R%26D%20Services/4.4.20%20Panel%20management/>). As it is presented in D2.1 Standard Version 1, a panel is a pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g., patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. Panel members have provided their contact details and other profiling information, which enables fast recruitment for specific research activities as they come up. Using the panel management software, it becomes easier for Living Labs to recruit, segment and maintain their panel or members. In addition to this, a panel management software allows panel managers to get insights quickly and easily from their panelists, create and manage a number of different panels, build rich profiles and also target segment of the panelist. A digital tool to manage all the contact information is mandatory, as it will reduce the management effort and provide valuable insights to the panel managers.

The panel management software provides features for storing, searching and identifying information that are used when a panel manager is communicating with the Living Lab panel. This information can include personal contact details for each member, previous interactions that have been done and details about the interaction. The manager can also schedule future interactions with the panel members. These interactions can be organized under events, that can be part of a larger project.

PaneLab is one such panel management tool developed and maintained by Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. It is a powerful community management tool designed to help efficiently manage communities. PaneLab features include the ability to contact and invite people for studies, organise logistics, keep track of ethics and informed consent signatures as well as a history of participated studies. The full functionality of the tool can be found through the website app.thepanelab.com, while through the application (currently deployed in Google play store) members can update their contact information, access their unique QR code card, as well as get invited, view their events and RSVP. Managers on the other hand can scan the QR code to note attendance and set the RSVP status.

3.1 Requirement elicitation methodology

To ensure that the Panel Management requirements were comprehensive and reflective of the needs of all stakeholders, a multi-faceted approach was taken. This involved sending out initially written introductions and follow-up emails, as well as conducting meetings with consortium members to gather input and insights on potential functionalities, existing bugs, improvements and suggestions for enhancing the usability of the tool. This approach was aimed at ensuring that all stakeholders were adequately consulted in the development of the requirements and that their feedback was appropriately considered in the final deliverable.

To foster collaboration and drive innovation in the project, a series of online and offline co-creation sessions and meetings were organized with community members and partners from other projects outside the consortium. These sessions provided a platform for stakeholders to share their knowledge and insights, with the goal of generating ideas and approaches to enhance the project outcomes. By engaging with a diverse range of stakeholders, we were able to capture the interest of the broader community and align more holistically with future needs.

3.2 Requirements

In the section below, we describe the updated list of requirements for the paneLab tool. We introduce some changes that were applied from the previous version (D2.8) and the newly requested features. This list includes requirements that are either already implemented in the system or planned to be delivered by the end of the project.

3.2.1 User Roles

PaneLab offers three user roles: Owner, Manager, and Member. The Owner is responsible for the specific organisation and all the procedures that the organisation performs in the panel management

tool. A Manager is assigned by the owner and can invite people or assign new managers. A Member is a stakeholder of the organisation that participates in projects, events and studies.

The VITALISE panel management tool ‘PaneLab’ will support various Living Labs, hereafter referred to as “organization” for the scope of software requirements.

The earlier categorization of two types of users, the “Admin User” and “Customer” as well as the user types of invited, applicant, seceder and exile are no longer used. An ‘Alumni’ user type will be applicable at a later stage. Taking that into account, we have identified the following user roles (Figure 1), for the panel management tool.

- **Owner:** the owner of an organization, the person responsible for the specific organization and all the procedures that the organization performs in the panel management tool
- **Manager:** the manager is assigned by the owner and is a user that can invite people to an organization or assign new managers.
- **Member:** a user that is an approved member of an organization. The member is a stakeholder of the organization that participates in projects, events and studies.

Figure 1 presents the changes that were applied compared to the previous requirements version (D2.8).

Applicant: a user that want to register in organisation by himself
Invited: a user that is invited by a *manager* to the organisation
Seceder: a user that left from organisation
Exile: a user that is banned from organisation by manager
Member: a user that is an approved member of organisation
Manager: a user that can invite people to an organisation
Owner: is the owner of an organisation

Figure 1 Panel management user types and the links among them

3.2.2 Actions Per Role for the web-based app

Through the performed workshops and the experience of Living Lab networks and AUTH, which is the main responsible for panel management, the following building blocks of the VITALISE panel management have been identified. Changes from the previous deliverable (D2.8) include addition of 'Groups' as well as removal of any actions related to user types that are no longer used.

Member Profile

- Contains all the information for a specific user, including: name, address, contact details, photo
- Contains information about the projects and events a member is participating in

Groups

- A group will include members of shared interests, demographics or attributes
- Members from groups will be able to get invited to new projects

Projects

- A project includes several activities, referred to as events
- The project should have an identity that is added from the beginning, including: name, start-end date, logo, ethical approval, consent template
- In project view, all the participants that have been tagged in the project should appear

Events

- One event can have several project tags (one event can be part of several projects) or untagged
- The event should have an identity that is added from the beginning, including: name, start-end date, project, place (map or zoom link)
- In event view, all the participants that have been tagged in the event should be seen

Based on those building blocks, we have identified specific actions per user role that are presented below and summarized also in Figure 2.

Owners

The owner can perform all the actions that a manager can do with the addition that the owner is the only user that can remove managers and update their profiles.

Manager

- As a manager, I want to search and see all the users that belong to my organisation
- As a manager, I want to view and update my own profile
- As a manager, I want to update the profiles of the members in my organization
- As a manager, I want to completely remove members from my organization
- As a manager, I want to invite managers/members to my organization

Managers would also like to have the following functionalities:

- As a manager, I would like to search all members in a project and open the personal contact details
- As a manager, I would like to search all members in an event and open the personal contact details
- As a manager, I would like to see the pending confirmations (about events' invitations)
- As a manager, I would like to search for members based on criteria:
 - Age group
 - Gender
 - Type of stakeholder (member tags e.g., older adults, doctor)
 - Available Means of communication (e.g., only people that are using viber)
 - Groups
 - Projects
 - Events

- Home address

Member

- As a member, I want to search and see the managers and owner that belong to my organisation
- As a member, I want to view and update my own profile
- As a member, I want to be able to leave from an organization

Figure 2 Panel management user actions per role

3.2.3 Actions per Role for the mobile app

The roles of owner, manager and member are maintained also in the mobile app. The user can connect with the same credentials as the web app and perform several actions as presented below:

- As a manager, I want to be able to see events and peoples RSVP
- As a manager, I want to be able to scan the cards of the participants in an event
- As a manager, I want to see my profile and my card
- As a member, I want to be able to get notifications about upcoming events
- As a member, I want to be able to see my events and RSVP
- As a member, I want to be able to see and update my profile
- As a member, I want to be able to see my card

3.2.4 Risks and motivators

Some of the challenges and motivators identified during the workshops as well as the written and verbal feedback are summarized here:

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- An important motivator is to create a tool that is easily integrated with all the other tools used by Living Lab researchers and managers in order to avoid losing time in changes among platforms.
- The member's user profile should go beyond simple demographic information and should include more details about the user (e.g. distinguish ambassadors, lead users, segmentation of panel, preferences in communication means)
- The tool should not be project-based as it increases the time needed to communicate with new people when a project ends.
- The wish for integration of documents and questionnaires within the tool was discussed. CMS is not within PaneLab's scope but option to add URL link to link with other sites to be considered
- Dashboard should be included that shows an overview of all the information and task to be done
- Analytics is a desired feature (participation rate, optimal contact rate, engagement score, etc.)
- Incorporation and signing of consent forms in the tool
- Email, app notification & SMS for contacting members (based on their preference) are valuable
- Send reminders if no RSVP from the member
- Members should be able to select their friends and then get a display of the number of their friends attending or having being invited to the event.
- Wish to keep pseudonymized IDs of persons & study datasets

4 AccelUp

One of the main objectives of VITALISE is to facilitate the growth and utilization of Health and Wellbeing Living Lab services, as well as Non-Health and Wellbeing Living Lab services, at local, trans-regional, and trans-national levels to support research and entrepreneurial products and services within the field. Despite the importance of Living Lab research and real environment testing infrastructures for researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain, Living Labs struggle to receive offers for private projects beyond their network due to the significant resources required to increase their visibility. Additionally, Living Labs often lack knowledge of how much to charge for their services, and researchers and research groups are sometimes unaware of Living Lab services, what they offer, and how to contact them. These issues have been identified by ENoLL and the Health and Wellbeing Action Oriented Task Force during meetups and individual discussions with Living Lab members.

The proposed AccelUp system aims to Increase visibility of Living Lab research and testing infrastructures and their services, attracting researchers, entrepreneurs and private companies. In that way, the Living Labs will be able to grow their activities and create a more sustainable business model as well as creating a portfolio of completed jobs and get insights on what the price for their services are (demand and offer will stabilize the prices). On the other hand, customers of Living Labs will be able to get qualified feedback regarding their research and/or products and services and even get a Living Lab certification that attaches a quality and reliability image to their products and services.

AccelUp has the mission to provide a unique value creating platform that opens living lab infrastructures and their services to the innovation ecosystem and research activities for the purpose of ensuring living lab customers can find a marketplace with labs that are able to provide the development, testing and certification bodies for their products.

4.1 Requirement elicitation methodology

VITALISE partners identified, studied, and explored existing freelancing and booking platforms, such as Freelancer.com and Booking.com, which systematize the service offerings of Language Service Providers (LLs) to independent clients. These platforms served as inspirations for the initial user requirements. Freelancer.com allows anyone to create an account as a recruiter or as a job seeker. When registering on the site, users are required to fill in their profile based on their job preferences (as shown in Figure 3). In each account, users can view both the jobs they have applied for and the jobs they are seeking employees for. Users also have a profile where they can add information about themselves and their skills, and the system automatically calculates Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) based on their performance. A similar platform is UpWork.com.

Figure 3 Freelancer first registration

Another widely used platform that was investigated for preparing the AccelUp system requirements, is the booking.com. In booking the user can post your accommodation facilities and make them available for people to rent. Users of the Booking.com can search based on various criteria (e.g., dates, facilities, price) and select the one that fits their needs.

Any company, research group or individual research will be able to post a description of an activity in AccelUp system as in freelancing platforms. Similar to Booking.com, they can also search for Living Labs and the previous works that they have done based on information that they provide and the KPIs that are manually calculated. The Living Labs of the network can assess the work that is required and make a bid. Then the customer can choose the bid that best fits its needs based on a set of criteria. This will be handled through a web platform, the AccelUp system, that will ensure the safe payment, completion of tasks and quality of services.

After that point, VITALISE partners continued the discussions on a bilateral basis in order to identify the and understand the AccelUp business case. To understand the business requirements of how Living Labs function with independent clients, a workshop was conducted during the plenary meeting in Vienna to validate a questionnaire that will be given to all ENOLL members (March 7th, 2023). With the exception of clients from EC or other funded initiatives where the LL is a member of a consortium, clients who contract work for LL services are referred to as “independent clients”. The following categories of independent clients were identified during the discussion: a) researchers; b) developers; c) business owners; d) SMEs/corporations; and e) other LLs. The topics discussed included a) the variety of independent client projects that LLs undertake each year, b) the typical (average) price that LLs charge for independent client projects, c) whether LLs have seen an increase or decrease in independent client projects, d) the different sources from which independent client projects come from, e) the approximate amount of money LLs pay each year to attract new clients, and f) whether the LLs are members of an organization that supports them in attracting new clients. The workshop resulted in the questionnaire's validation, and the next stage is to distribute the survey to all ENOLL members to gain insight on the aforementioned business aspects.

4.2 Requirements

4.2.1 User Roles

The main user roles that are identified for the AccelUp system are summarized below:

- **Super user:** is responsible for the entire system and its smooth operation.
- **Assigners:** Organizations (SMEs, academia, industry etc.) looking for someone to complete/assign a work/project
- **Freelancers (Living Labs):** Organizations (basically Living Labs) that are undertaking the work/project
- **Investors:** investors can see projects that have bids but do not have budget from the assigners and can provide the money for the implementation. This role is not included in the current implementation but is envisaged to be implemented in future prototypes of the system

4.2.2 Actions Per Role

Through discussions with experts in the field and considering the functionalities offered by similar tools, we have identified the following requirements for each role. These requirements are updated from the previous version (D2.8) and reflect the current version of the system and the requirements that are planned to be delivered until the end of the project.

Super user

- As a super user, I want to be able to add or remove expertise fields.
- As a super user, I want to be able to add or remove offered services.
- As a super user, I want to be able to ban any user that does not comply with the community rules.
- As a super user, I want to approve or disapprove the authorization requests of freelancers by clicking a button.
- Super User will have access to all information in the system, regardless of if they are sealed or private for an account.

Assigners/ project creators

- As an assigner, I want to be able to change basic information on my profile or delete them.
- As an assigner I want to see information my projects (open, terminated or accepted)
- As an assigner, I want to define a project that I want to be undertaken including things like:
 - Name
 - General description
 - Required services (from a list)

- Estimated budget (min / max) – hourly budget (optional)
- Region/location of interest (optional)
- Attach file (images or documents) (optional)
- As an assigner, I want to be able to choose if my project will be publicly available or available only to authorized freelancers.
- As an assigner, I want to select if the bids for my project will be publicly available or sealed. Sealed bids can be seen only by me and the Super User.
- As an assigner I want to limit the number of offers I will accept.
- As an assigner I want to set expiration for accepting bids.
- As an assigner, I want to receive all bids that are made for my project in a list.
- As an assigner I want to be able to change my project details.
- As an assigner, I want to see other projects that have been posted from other assigners.
- As an assigner I want to accept a bid at any time. If a bid is accepted the project is set to winner selected.
- If no offer fits my needs, I want to be able close/terminate the project.
- As an assigner I can receive messages from freelancers that have made a bid for my project
- As an assigner I can ask for more information from freelancers that have placed a bid via the message option
- As an assigner, I want to be able to post a comment for the freelancers that have completed a work and a simple rate (e.g., 1-5 stars)

Freelancers actions

- As a freelancer, I want to be able to update basic information on my profile or delete them.
- As a freelancer I want to see in one page the available projects that are related to my expertise and provided services.
- As a freelancer, I want to see the projects that I have undertaken (past projects)
- As a freelancer I want to see my bids (open, closed and approved)
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to place a bid for a project by adding information like estimated cost, estimated days, expertise of people involved and general description (optional)
- As a freelancer I want to see other available bids for the projects that do not have sealed bids
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to filter the projects posted based on categories
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to change my bid at any time while the project is open for bids.
- As a freelancer, I want to contact assigners by sending a message to request further information about a project. A message can be sent only when a bid is made.
- As a freelancer I want to receive a notification when a project that I have placed a bid for, have some information changes.
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to withdraw my bid at any time until it is selected by the assigner.
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to post a comment and rate for the assigners that I completed I work for

Investors

The investors type and requirements is not yet implemented in the system. The use case will be validated from business perspective in order to decide for its final inclusion.

- As an investor, I want to see the projects that are tagged as “looking for investors” and already have bids from freelancers. Projects that are tagged as “looking for investors” but do not have bids, will not be available for investment.
- As an investor, I want to select the preferable bid for the project that I am going to invest in.

4.2.3 Risks and motivators

Some of the key points that are requested by Living Labs to be considered when designing the AccelUp system are:

- A Living Lab might not be able to undertake a whole project by his own and might not be able to address the issue. We should be able to combine more than one Living Lab for a specific demand
- We must try to raise everyone up and not create services for maintaining some at the top
- Involvement of more mature and experienced Living Labs with less mature ones and try to learn from each other
- It is difficult for a Living Lab to operate in other countries, especially in the healthcare sector where “standards” change among countries. Living Labs can help external companies to explore the local culture.
- We should be careful not to drop prices too much as some Living Lab might have lower prices than others
- We should invest on the element of community and balance, offer what each Living Lab would like to do and what they know
- Living Labs operate with different business models and pricing structures.
- Some Living Labs may not be able to engage in for-profit activities such as those projects which come in as requests.
- Living Labs are very protective of their networks and may be unwilling to collaborate with other Living Labs

5 RAI system and Discovery portal

VITALISE proposes to open access to Living Labs' captured data for processing, enabling open, fair and reliable Research Community where every researcher will be accredited for their work and all research data will be equally accessible for processing without violating data protection regulations. In this sense, VITALISE introduces the Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) and the VITALISE e-infrastructure that will support research and data analysis services.

The RAI identifier is aimed at becoming an immutable identifier for a reliable research experiment results referencing, which include information on the experiment dataset, processing script, authorship, timing and produced results, encrypted and stored within a blockchain network. In few words it's aimed to become, the DOI of the scientific results analysis.

The VITALISE e-infrastructure's main components are the RAI Certified Nodes, the Discovery portal (depicted as RAI Finder Service in the figure below), and the RAI Cloud Server (depicted as RAI Registration Service in the figure below).

The RAI Certified Nodes are going to be installed in each living lab and are responsible for (1) collecting, preparing and transforming data (for each living lab) into harmonised VITALISE data model, (2) informing and updating Discovery portal on data available for research, (3) generating synthetic data (representing real data) to allow researchers to developed algorithm locally on their PCs, (4) executing external researchers developed algorithms with the real data, (5) requesting scientific results registration upon external researchers request.

The discovery portal is the common entry point for external researchers to (1) query and identify Living Lab available research data, (2) interact with the RAI Certified Node containing the data of interest, for getting a synthetic version of the data, for remotely testing locally developed algorithms with real data and registering results, and (3) to resolve and identify research assets and information for a given RAI identifier. Additionally, the discovery portal is the common entry point for the different VITALISE ICT tools.

The RAI Cloud Server is responsible for guaranteeing the perdurance of research analysis results in time and registering the information and research assets involved in a scientific experiment, upon a researchers request. These assets and information will be encrypted and written into blockchain network, producing a RAI identifier.

Figure 4 RAI system overview

5.1 Requirement elicitation methodology

In order to collect requirements regarding the RAI system, two types of interviews were conducted, one addressing researchers with and one without technical background. Members of the consortium

as well as external researchers were considered for the interviews. The inclusion criteria for them to fall into the “technical background” category, was relevant experience with data acquisition, storage, handling and analysis. In Appendix 1 we present the list of question for both types of interviews. An interview in the form of a focus group was conducted in AUTH, in order to refine the questions which were used in the one-on-one interviews with the partners of the consortium or external researchers.

In total, four technical and four non-technical interviews were conducted, via video-conference calls. Interviewees from the consortium provided verbal consent for session recording, whereas non-members had to provide signed written consent. The information was consolidated after the end of the sessions and the requirements elicited through the interviews, are presented in Sections 5.2 and 6.2.

5.2 Requirements

Collaboration and data exchange have been hampered due to 2 major factors: the lack of data standardisation and harmonisation, and the challenges of data security and privacy, which are of particular relevance in the context of medical data. To address these challenges, we developed a system that embraces the concept of data model (5.2.1) and protected data sharing (5.2.2), allowing Researchers to share sensitive data in a safe and standard way and to explore other datasets for developing and improving their work. Below, we present the final version of requirements for the whole RAI system addressing the different sub-systems. Namely, we present the requirements that were taken into account for the design of the data model, the final version of the RAI system architecture and the discovery portal that enables users to search and identify existing datasets.

5.2.1 Data Model

The VITALISE Data Model, already developed, addresses the data standardisation and harmonisation challenge with its potential for extension. Every allowed type of measurement is well-defined in this schema.

The available upload data options to the RAI Node include heart rate and steps measurements from a Fitbit device, which are then transformed to the VITALISE Data Model, and data points or data arrays in the conformant VITALISE Data Model standard. This will allow datasets of measurement sessions to be successfully stored in the Node and be further processed as mentioned in the 2.8 Deliverable.

5.2.2 RAI system

The RAI Certified Node is designed as a technical tool for Researchers and Living Lab Data Analysts. for data management. It is conceived as a local implementation (1) to protect the security and privacy of sensible data, ensuring ownership and compliance with legal provisions on this regard, (2) to allow a safe way of data sharing, making valuable data as open as possible under each institution/organization control, and (3) to contribute on the harmonisation of data and reproducibility of results in research.

RAI Certified Node general requirements and installation are described in the deliverable D3.6, and the following table reflects the current functionalities available:

Table 1 RAI Certified Nodes available functionalities divided into categories

Category		RAI Certified Nodes available functionalities
Datasets	Registration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Person registration (optional for uploading): this function allows the Researcher to register a subject introducing only 2 inputs (both mandatory): (1) gender and (2) birthday. Then, a unique identifier is generated for this subject, and this identifier can be linked to the participant measurements. 2. Dataset registration (mandatory for uploading): this function allows the Researcher to register a dataset of measurements

		<p>introducing 4 (mandatory) inputs: (1) indicate if the dataset is anonymised (true) or not (false), (2) a description of the dataset to make clear what type of data contains the dataset, (3) name of the dataset, which should be also indicative of what type of data or which study this dataset is part of, and (4) the author or researcher responsible for the dataset. Following, a unique identifier for the dataset is generated, and associated measurements can be upload using this unique identifier.</p>
	<p>Upload</p>	<p>3. Upload datasets: to upload measurements, it is optional to link them to a person identifier but mandatory to associate them to a dataset identifier. When the identifier(s) is/are available, there are currently 4 options to upload data:</p> <p>Vitalise Data Point: this option allows to upload a data point that follows the specific structure of the VITALISE Data Model (json structure). When the format is validated, a confirmation message indicates that the data point has been correctly stored.</p> <p>Vitalise Data Array: this option allows to upload a data array composed of several data points, all of them having the specific structure of the VITALISE Data Model (json structure). This is a generalisation of the data point uploading. When the format is validated, a confirmation message indicates that the data array has been correctly stored. Currently, the VITALISE Data Model supports heart rate and steps data types, and it is projected to support further data types.</p> <p>Fitbit Heart Rate and Steps: this option allows to upload a dataset of heart rate measurements using a Fitbit device. Fitbit measurements follow a specific structure that is then convert to the VITALISE Data Model (json structure). When the format is validated, a confirmation message indicates that the heart rate measurements have been correctly stored.</p> <p>There is support for multiple sensor types (i.e., Fitbit & VITALISE data model uploaded (limited)) experiments</p> <p>4. NDM Data: this function, which stands for Non data model (NDM) compliant version, allows the uploading of .csv files without specific structure for anonymised datasets. This means, the data measurements do not follow the established VITALISE Data Model or the Fitbit data types specified (heart rate nor steps). To upload a NDM dataset, there are 4 (mandatory) inputs: (1) a description of the dataset to make clear what type of data contains the dataset, (2) name of the dataset, which should be also indicative of what type of data or which study this dataset is part of, (3) the author or researcher responsible for the dataset, and (4) a .csv file containing the dataset itself. Due to the flexibility of the file structure for this option, there are limited functionalities available for this workflow.</p>
	<p>Workflow</p>	<p>5. Anonymised Data: this function allows for external users to request uploaded datasets that were tagged as anonymised (anonymised option as true). The user can implement filters regarding subject's metadata, such gender and/or birthday. Once a dataset is requested, a unique identifier is generated. With this</p>

		<p>unique identifier, the user can retrieve the anonymised dataset in .csv or .json format according to preferences.</p> <p>6. Synthetic Data: this function allows for external users to request the generation of synthetic data from uploaded datasets that were tagged as non-anonymised (anonymised option as false). The user can implement filters regarding subject's metadata, such gender and/or birthday for selecting the data that the model will train on for generating the synthetic data. Once the synthetic dataset is available, a unique identifier is generated. With this unique identifier, the user can retrieve the synthetic dataset in .csv or .json format according to preferences. This function does not apply to the NDM Data option.</p> <p>7. NDM Data: additional functions for this option includes the possibility to explore uploaded datasets, request datasets with the corresponding unique identifier, and request an available dataset.</p> <p>8. View available datasets general statistics: descriptive features of each dataset are available by requesting it so the interested user can assess general sample characteristics.</p>
Analysis	Remote Execution	<p>9. Upload and run scripts on available datasets: it is possible to implement processing pipelines by creating scripts that can be uploaded and ran on the selected datasets from a specific RAI Node. This generates a unique experiment identifier, which is then used for retrieving the results of the experiment.</p> <p>10. Results registration (optional): if the Researcher is satisfied with the results after running a script, this function allows to register those results using the experiment identifier so other users can examine them.</p>
	Get results	<p>11. Access results of ran scripts: registered results can be inquired by other users using the experiment identifier.</p>
	Programming language	<p>12. RAI system supports data analysis using Python scripts</p>

5.2.3 Discovery portal

The Discovery Portal is a cloud-based platform that is designed to facilitate the discovery and use of data resources across the VITALISE ecosystem. This portal serves as a central hub for accessing metadata catalogs that contain indexed datasets, both anonymized and non-anonymized, based on the VITALISE Data Model in T3.2 and Non Data Model (NDM) formats.

One of the main features of the Discovery Portal is its ability to support the discovery and exploration of data. This is achieved by providing researchers with search capabilities that allow them to discover for data based on a range of criteria, including keyword, gender and birth date. The Discovery Portal features user-friendly interfaces that allow users to examine, display, and download data in a variety of formats. Another important aspect of the Discovery Portal is that it provides the opportunity for researchers to request and obtain Synthetic Data. It also facilitates the communication between researchers and the VITALISE RAI Nodes for experiment submission and registration.

The goal of the Discovery Portal is to include federated authentication and authorization of its users across the VITALISE system, to integrate advanced search features and to provide analytics with information regarding the use of the system amongst the research community.

Figure 5 - Discovery Portal System

Table 2 provides an overview of the user-related functionalities of the Discovery Portal for the **Administrator** and **Processor** (Researcher) user roles. The Administrator role has access to all functionalities of the portal, including user management, content management, and analytics. The Processor role, on the other hand, has limited access and can only register a new RAI Node, search, visualise and request for data, submit experiment for remote execution and register experiment results.

Table 2 - Discovery Portal User-related functionalities

User Role	Functionality
Administrator	View Analytics through the Discovery Portal Dashboard
Processor	Register to the Discovery Portal
Administrator & Processor	Login to the Discovery Portal
Administrator & Processor	Register a new RAI Node to the Discovery Portal
Administrator & Processor	Search & visualise Metadata registered by all the available RAI Nodes of the VITALISE System
Administrator & Processor	Request & retrieve Synthetic Data generation from a specific set of non-anonymised, data model compliant data by a selected RAI Node
Administrator & Processor	Request & retrieve non-data model compliant datasets by a selected RAI Node
Administrator & Processor	Submit a specific a python script, the requirements file of the script and the configuration file of the script for remote execution to a selected RAI Node
Administrator & Processor	Receive & retrieve experiment results for the submitted experiment
Administrator & Processor	Register experiment results to the VITALISE System

5.2.4 User Roles (RAI System)

As previously mentioned, the VITALISE e-infrastructure’s main components are the RAI Certified Nodes, the Discovery portal, and the RAI Cloud Server. The RAI Certified nodes are to be installed in each living lab and only specific personnel may interact with them. The Discovery portal is the main application that will allow researchers to interact with the rest of the system. The RAI Cloud Server operates in the background, thus there are no direct interactions with the users.

Based on this 3 components infrastructure, the outcomes from the previous deliverable (D2.8), and the current implementation of the system, the identified user roles can be described as:

- **Controller:** The “owner” of the datasets uploaded from a Living Lab and the manager of the RAI Certified Node installed in a Living Lab. Users that may undertake the responsibilities of this role are: Living Lab/Data manager, Project/Pilot manager, Panel manager, Business developer of the Living Lab, Information Specialist/Librarian.
- **Processor (Researcher):** Individuals (or organizations) that wish to gain access to and process the uploaded datasets through the Discovery portal. User types under the umbrella of this role are:
 - External researcher, i.e., researchers that do not belong to an organization or institute with direct access to a RAI Certified Node, but wish to perform an analysis, as well as researchers that belong to an organization or institute with direct access to a RAI Certified Node, but wish to perform analysis on datasets belonging to another RAI Certified node.
 - Teachers that may use datasets or the system for educational purposes.
- **Administrator:** The technical partner(s) responsible for the operation and maintenance of the system,
- **Public:** Individuals that have no active role in the processing of datasets. Users pertaining to this role may be:
 - Journal editors
 - Members of the public

5.2.5 Actions per role (RAI System)

Controllers should usually perform their actions through the RAI Certified Nodes and through indirect interactions with the RAI Cloud Server. Controllers can also interact with the Discovery Portal and access all available functionalities there. Processors (Researchers) may execute their actions only through the Discovery Portal, interacting with the rest of the system though background operation. The administrator may interact with all components of the system, while public users may perform their limited actions through the Discovery Portal.

Controller

Table 3 Controller actions

Category		As a controller, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Registration	1. Register a person (subject/patient) 2. Register a dataset
	Upload	3. Upload datasets that follow a model compliant format 4. Upload datasets that do not have a model compliant format (NDM Data) 5. Provide access to other researchers to upload their own datasets (become a controller) 6. Manage the metadata of the datasets I have uploaded

		7. Describe the level of privacy of the data included in the uploaded dataset (if they are fully anonymized or not)
	Search/View	8. View all datasets in the network
	Other	9. Install the RAI node in a local computer through easy steps
Analysis	Upload script	10. View and/or check the scripts uploaded by researchers for the analysis of datasets I have uploaded
	Run script	11. Upload and run scripts on available datasets 12. Register results
	Get results	13. Access results of ran scripts
	Resolve RAI Identifier	14. Verify RAI identifiers

Processor (Researcher)

Table 4 Processor actions

Category		As a processor, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	1. Become a controller, i.e., upload my own datasets on a RAI Certified node
	Search/View	2. Search available datasets and view general features 3. Search for available datasets based on metadata
	Synthetic data	4. Request synthetic data for a specific dataset 5. Receive synthetic data for a specific dataset 6. View metrics related to the quality of the synthetic data 7. Choose the synthetic data format type (csv or json)
	Other	8. Have access to both quantitative and qualitative data 9. Share a link to a dataset
Analysis	Upload script	10. Choose a dataset of interest and upload a script file to perform my preferred analysis
	Run script	11. Develop and run locally script on synthetic data before initiating the actual analysis 12. Run a script on multiple datasets from the same RAI node 13. Receive feedback on the running process of my analysis
	Get results	14. View the results of my analysis

		15. Download my results in a format of my choosing (csv or json)
	Resolve RAI Identifier	16. Resolve RAI identifiers for the authentication of my analysis

Administrator

Table 5 Administrator actions

Category		As an administrator, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	1. Add and remove users
	Search/View	2. Govern the approval process for a processor to gain access to a dataset
	Synthetic data	<i>No action considered for this role as of yet</i>
	Other	3. Grant access rights to controllers
Analysis	<i>Not applicable</i>	

Public User

Table 6 Public user actions

Category		As a public user, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	<i>Not applicable</i>
	Search/View	
	Synthetic data	
	Other	1. View publications that have used one or more datasets
Analysis	Upload script	<i>Not applicable</i>
	Run script	
	Get results	
	Resolve RAI Identifier	2. Verify the analysis and its results
	Other	<i>No action considered for this role as of yet</i>

6 Sensors' integration system

A sensors integration server was developed as an iterative prototype, to provide a central infrastructure, where device-specific plugins are used for data gathering. The server is deployed on a Raspberry PI, through a custom image distribution. In the same image, an MQTT broker is set up to achieve the data flow of Figure 5. The use is as follows: There is a device-specific plugin, which handles the connection with the sensor and publishes all the resulting data, extended with date-time information, in VITALISE compliant JSON objects to the locally set up MQTT Broker. The topics of publishing follow a tree structure of measurement (super category – category – device BLE/MAC address (in the form of 6 bytes separated by colons – e.g. `00:00:00:aa:11:22`). The next plugin in the data flow is the listener, which subscribes to topics of interest, with the use of keywords, which could point to a device, a type of measurement or both. It receives the data and on stop, it saves them locally and registers and posts the dataset (and the person if applicable) to the RAI Node.

Figure 6: Schematic representation of data flow in the Sensors Integration Server

An example of the tree structure of MQTT topics is presented below, for a sample oximeter device which provides two different types of measurements:

```

vitalise
├── physiological_monitoring
│   ├── heart_rate
│   └── oximeter_BLE_address
└── biometrics
    ├── blood_oxygen
    └── oximeter_BLE_address
  
```

In order to prepare a proof-of-concept example, the listener and oximeter plugins were developed to reach the functionality of the server depicted in Figure 6, by connecting to the respective device, gathering measurements, and following the data flow in general, in order to further develop the prototype, the documentation, etc. in an iterative approach. In Figure 7, the main view (dashboard) and the plugin configuration view of the server are presented. Note that it is deployed and accessible on the localhost address; the same holds for the MQTT Broker. On the right, the plugin parameters are provided through free text.

Figure 7 Server main and plugin configuration views

6.1 Requirement Elicitation methodology

The interviews used for the RAI system (Section 5.1) also helped to identify requirements regarding the sensors integration server. The requirements identified, are presented in Section 6.2.

Additionally, to further refine the function and UX of the server, two demonstrations and workshop were implemented. The first in the Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Laboratory in AUTH and the second in a virtual conference with the participation of partners from all VITALISE Living Labs. The server has also been presented and discussed in the plenary.

In the first demonstration, three researchers with technical background and experience in infrastructure setup and measurement gathering participated. In the second demonstration, the participants were also required to have the two above qualifications, at least one from each Living Lab, but it was also open to researchers without these two requirements, from the respective LLs. The sessions were recorded after acquiring verbal consent, in order for members of the LLs to distribute it to their technical colleagues who were not present, so that they could also provide their feedback. A follow-up email was sent, providing the link to the recording. The Sensors Integration server was demonstrated in both cases and was set-up on a Raspberry. Aside from the server dashboard, the function was displayed with two plugins, one gathering measurements from a BerryMed oximeter and posting them to an MQTT Broker, and the listener gathering measurements from the Broker and posting them to the RAI Node. Feedback was acquired and used for the compilation of the requirements below.

6.2 Requirements

From the interviews, requirements were elicited regarding sensor usage and consequent plugin development prioritization, technical constraints on interfacing and local storage, infrastructure monitoring, data schema, measurements granularity and scaling, UI, documentation, reuse of configurations per subject and potential deployment on different platforms. In the following sections we present the requirements that are actually implemented or will be implemented in the system by the end of the project. Specific sensors are or will become available for integrations through developed plugins by the end of the project and are presented below. Also, we present requirements regarding the data schema, its integration to the system, data granularity, user interface and the role of the server administrator.

6.2.1 User Roles

The user roles that were identified for guaranteeing the proper use of the infrastructure are two, the user and the administrator.

- **Administrator:** The user tasked with ensuring the seamless functioning of the infrastructure, acting as a technical liaison between the users and the developers.
- **User:** Any internal or external researcher conducting studies, using existing devices and their respective plugins in the Living Lab.

6.2.2 Actions per role

Through the guided interviews and demonstrations that took place, for the two roles identified, the relevant action requirements have also been elicited.

User

- As a user I want to use the infrastructure to gather measurements and produce datasets
- As a user I want these datasets to be accessible so that I can transfer them to another device to run analyses on them
- As a user I want to be guided to achieve the gathering and transfer of the measurements

Administrator

- As an administrator I need to be updated on the infrastructure through documentation and/or support from the developers
- As an administrator I need to provide support to the users and introduce them to the use of the infrastructure
- As an administrator I need to ensure seamless functionality of the infrastructure and troubleshoot potential problems

6.2.3 List of sensors

Through the interviews, various sensors have been identified to be used by the research groups of the interviewees, either casually or circumstantially. This information was also complemented by the list of sensors used in VITALISE Joint Research Activities and by the collection of sensors used in each Living Lab that was included in the VITALISE Open Calls material. All the sensors gathered, were prioritized based on the frequency of use. The final list of sensors and applications which are commonly used between the LLs and of which at least 3 will be chosen for their respective plugin implementation, according to their necessity, is presented in the following list:

- Fitbit tracker
- Smart scales (Withings)
- Thermometers (Beurer, Withings)
- Inertial Measurement Units (TEA Captiv, XSens, APDM)
- Body Composition Analyzers (Tanita)
- Pulse oximeters (Berrymed, Medisana)

Since the server is modular and device-agnostic, as per requirements, plugins could be developed, either by the device manufacturers or the researchers, and integrated easily in it. A focus will be given to the above list, but not in a stringent manner. The interfacing with the devices has been identified to include Bluetooth (Low Energy) and the manufacturer's Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), e.g., the Fitbit API.

6.2.4 Data schema

In the interviews, the issue of schema and informative dataset metadata use has been repeatedly brought up. The VITALISE Data Model addresses the issue of schema. This leads to the specification of the plugins output, in order to conform to the Data Model. Further updates to the schema could include additional types of measurements. In this case, special care should be exercised concerning the continuous integration of the model updates into the plugins. Regarding the issue of informative metadata, the researcher provides dataset descriptions in the listener configuration. At the moment, a liberal description could be used as input. This should be further

addressed in a new workshop to either reach consensus on a manner describing datasets and how liberal or constraint this input can be.

6.2.5 Granularity of data

The sampling and time intervals that should be accounted for, are in the orders of milliseconds and months, respectively. Since the server is decoupled from the devices through plugins, the first requirement should be addressed individually per device plugin. For the second requirement, the listener plugin should consider constraints of local storage memory and periodically post the gathered data to the RAI Node.

6.2.6 Simultaneous connections - Scaling

The demonstration conducted with technical staff of AUTH, revealed the constraint of simultaneous Bluetooth / BLE interfacing with a Raspberry Pi. This is due to the OS handling of Bluetooth connections and should be addressed with explicit instructions per use-case and plugin development. The final consideration, which should be at least inspected, is the possibility of a continuous stream plugin to unblock the BLE interface for a hit-and-run plugin, which conveys a few bytes of information and terminates. This is evaluated as a more difficult to implement requirement. Prioritization should take place according to the ratio of necessity over cost. Finally, as a result of the demonstration, the requirement to explicitly document the above limitations of the system arose. This came up as a necessary provision, by the participants in the demonstration and should be prioritized. Scaling was also a concern in the second demonstration.

6.2.7 User interface

For the UI of the server, the following requirements have been identified:

1. Providing a view of configurations on currently active plugins, to inspect possible misconfigurations.
2. Providing a view on at least a logging level of “error” per plugin configuration, in order to inspect misconfigurations which cause the plugin to terminate abnormally.
3. Front-end validation of well-defined configuration fields.

These requirements resulted from the demonstration of the server. The 3rd observation, on server-side, should work closely with the plugins, which provide their configurations in json files. Currently, the configuration fields are provided in free text, and special care should be exercised over typographic errors. In cases where the fields could be predefined (e.g. in the listener plugin for the gender attribute of the subject), this should be addressed as to alleviate the user of the concern of entering improper values. The rest putative mistakes should be addressed with the 1st and 2nd observations.

6.2.8 Deployment of the server on different platforms

The possibility to deploy the sensors integration server on a VM, or remotely, was brought up in the second demonstration. In principle, the server could be deployed on everything where the appropriate versions of Node.js and specific libraries exist. This option might not exist for the compiled releases provided. Aside from that, the plugins, irrespectively of the developer, should specifically state the platform and architecture for which they are released. Support, at least initially, will only be provided for the Raspberry Pi architectures. Limitations would exist on the functionality of the plugins used, which would require access to physical interfaces of the machine, such as Bluetooth adapters, USB ports etc. For plugins that function with APIs, in principle, there should be no limitation on the extended functionality of the server that they provide. The other case is deploying the Raspberry remotely, e.g. to a subject’s home and plugins would then be initiated on researcher’s will. This, in theory, would also be possible, again with exposing the Raspberry on the internet, but in this case, additional security measures mitigating risks of data breach should be addressed beforehand.

6.2.9 Logic in the Listener Plugin

One requirement regards the use of the same person for a study. This can only be addressed with a new variant of configuration for the listener plugin. This could be accomplished by separating the logic of the existing listener. The one available at the time of writing this, would register a new dataset and a new user each time it was run (that means different UUIDs in the RAI server), even if the data refer to a dataset or person for which another instance of the listener has been executed in past time. This modification would require two things:

1. Pre-registering the dataset and person (if applicable) directly with the RAI Node API.
2. Specifying in the configuration the UUIDs provided by the RAI Node through registering.

The facts that this requirement is irrelevant to the server application as well as that in this workflow, the process is not completely realized through the application interface, since it involves accessing the API beforehand for acquiring the UUIDs, should be noted.

6.2.10 Technical Liaison

The participants in the demonstration also proposed the role of the administrator, who will be trained to use and troubleshoot any problems with the server. This person is the liaison between the developers of this infrastructure and the end-users (researchers in the LLs). As previously identified in the D2.8 deliverable, this role could be undertaken by the “Controller” of the RAI Node (see 3.3.1.1 *Section – User Roles* in D2.8).

7 Conclusion

This Deliverable presents the final version of VITALISE ICT tools user requirements for the four tools that are the outcomes of VITALISE WP3, namely: the panel management, the AccelUp system, the RAI system and Discovery portal and the sensors' integration system. The requirements were based on the demonstrations of advanced systems to the end users with a combination of interviews with experts to identify their needs. The requirements presented in this deliverable are either implemented or will be added in the systems by the end of the project. This deliverable offers a good overview of the overall functionalities of VITALISE ICT tools from a user perspective.

The PaneLab tool, is currently deployed in all VITALISE Living Labs and it is also offered to external projects for free, in order to finalize the beta testing. The first collected feedback helped us to structure the roadmap for the next releases and also introduce a new mobile app for enhancing user engagement. AccelUp tool currently offers all the main functionality and the upcoming work will focus on the business and exploitation perspective and gathering feedback from first adopters. The RAI system and sensors integration will be deployed soon in the VITALISE Living Labs that will act as beta testers. The RAI system will also support VITALISE Virtual Access that will start in the upcoming months. AUTH will continue monitoring users's feedback for the various tools in order to create an updated set of requirements that will feed the exploitation plans for each tool.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 – Questionnaire on attitudes of researchers on data sharing

The following questions were agreed upon in order to conduct the semi-structured interviews.

Technical-related Questions

Possible interviewees: Researchers working with data acquisition, storage, handling, analysis.

1. Please describe an experiment in which you used a sensor/digital device for data collection. Guide me through the process of deployment, installation, data gathering, data handling, storage and analysis.
2. Can you describe to us a typical sensor setup that you performed, including its configuration for use and interfacing with a network (via pc, smartphone etc.)?
3. What software do you use for interfacing and measurement gathering? Is it vendor specific (and how much is its cost) or home-made? Is it an API (more probable with vendor spec. software)? Have you tried finding an open solution first? What is your view about it?
4. If it is vendor specific and the data is offered through the cloud, what challenges did you face in order to gain access to this data? Were there any concerns about privacy?
5. If you developed the software, does it concern a) data gathering, b) harmonization, c) data exchange? Have you searched for existing solutions first?
6. In the experiments that you have performed so far, were you interested in real-time data or aggregated (averages per day/hour e.g.)?
7. What software do you usually use for your measurements analysis (excel, python, js, spss, etc.)?
8. How long do your experiment sessions usually last (hours/days)? If there was an interruption in your data gathering, how long should it last, for you to consider your session failed?
9. Have you collaborated previously with any other LL or research team/lab regarding data gathering, exchange and harmonization? If yes, what was the time, effort and cost you had to invest?
10. What was the biggest challenge that you faced when trying to unify/integrate data from different devices into a common dataset? Do you follow a standard as a laboratory, or does it depend on the experiment?